

Project coordinator

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Novel packaging films and textiles with tailored
end of life and performance based on bio-based
copolymers and coatings

Key figures

Call topic: BBI.2018.SO3.R10

Develop bio-based packaging products that are biodegradable/ compostable and/or recyclable

4 years (1/06/2019 – 31/05/2023)

Budget € 5,4M (BBI-JU contribution 4,2M€)

"Biontop consortium complementary expertise"

21 partners (4 Research and Technology Organisations, 9 SMEs, 6 Large Industries, a consumers' association and a pan EU industry association)

7 Biobased Industries Consortium members

8 countries

Objectives

In view of the insufficient packaging recycling rate and deficient biodegradable packaging properties for demanding applications, Biontop will develop new bio-copolymers, compounds, biocomposites & coatings formulation and process them into:

- **Recyclable, home-compostable monomaterial trays & films** for F&V (fruit and vegetables).
- **Recyclable, multilayer trays & films compatible with MAP** (modified atmosphere packaging), e.g. **dairy and personal care products**.
- **Home compostable & organically recyclable nets** for F&V.
- **Home compostable & organically recyclable coated textiles**.
- **Recyclable, reusable coated woven fabrics**, e.g. **food wraps**.
- **Recyclable, reusable secondary packaging** from SRM (secondary raw material): **extruded blown bags and non-woven bags**.

"Routes of bio-based sustainable packaging material"